

THE SUBJECT MATTER AND IMAGERY OF THE "MISERABLE EYES".

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Аннотация: Ушбу мақолада болалар ёзувчиси Х.Тўхтабоевнинг "Мунгли кўзлар" романининг мавзу кўлами ва тасвир услуби, асарнинг яратилиш тарихи, сюжет, конфликт ва ечимнинг ўзига хослиги тадқиқ қилинган.

Калит сўзлар: Роман, бадиий асар мавзуси, бадиий асар зояси, бадиий тасвир, ёзувчи тасвир услуби.

Annotation: This article states the scope and style of the theme of the novel "Miserable Eyes" by children's writer H. Tukhtaboev, the history of the work, the plot, the conflict and the specificity of the solution.

Keywords: Novel, fiction novel, idea of novel, artistic image, style of the writer's image.

Аннотация: В данной статье рассматриваются объем и стиль темы романа детского писателя Х. Тухтабоева «Грустные глаза», а так же история создания произведения, сюжет, конфликт и специфика решения.

Ключевые слова: Роман, тема художественного произведения, идея художественного произведения, художественный образ, стиль образа писателя.

The novel "Miserable Eyes" was published in 1988. It is more accurate to say that the work is a product of the last years of the Soviet regime. In 1985-1990, the press had the opportunity to say whatever it wanted, especially bribery among Soviet officials, the judiciary and traders, the growing public outcry over their artificial deficits, and repression. It is a well-known fact that the sudden emergence of so much hidden information has led to many publicist speeches in the spirit of revelation, and even in fiction, a number of works led by the spirit of revelation.

In deed, it means that many negative information about the socio-economic life of H. Tukhtaboev, collected during his feuilleton activity, also served as material for the creation of this work.

Most of the readers of "Miserable Eyes" are mainly arguing around a strange question: Who is Akbar? Donomi, stupid? True, his parents are superstitious, selfish, and outgoing scammers. But, anyway, one is father, one is mother! For Akbar, they are even willing to risk their lives. The boy, who had not seen the hadith, wrote a complaint against them and imprisoned them. Now what face can people look at? What will happen in the afterlife? " [1.65]

In fact, as you have finish reading the novel, it is natural that a thousand different thoughts will flood your mind. The novel is about a mother (Yakutkhan) who can tell the quality of gold at a glance, a father whose heart is always burning with love for gold, and a

father (Saidjon) who, as a warehouse manager, considers it legal to take a pledge for each item sold from shopkeepers. It happens around the family past of children who have different views on how to get rich in such ways. While Akbar, the eldest son of a disabled man, considers his father to be a bribe-taker and his mother to be a speculator, Zafar, a second son, considers them needy. While Akbar strongly condemns his parents' actions as espionage and bribery, Zafar sees bribery in the example of neighboring officials as not a crime but a daily occurrence in society.

The writer came to the city from a distant village to study, but witnessed injustices during his admission to the university. He convincingly describes the fate of Saidjon, who came to the conclusion that his work ended with a bribe of three thousand soums, and that all work would end with money.

The first example: "Three children from our village went to school. I was the one with the most knowledge between us. After all, I studied with them, I knew what it was worth. No, they passed, I stayed. One of them, your uncle Shakir, who still comes to our house, brought his children in the winter, and he would show his nose wherever he said. His father was a farm manager, he was rich, he had a lot of money, he talked to five thousand people. If I'm a galvars, I'm going to get into a fight with the rector. Our second friend came and landed right at a friend's house. His intention moved easily. Worst of all, both of my friends would not hide from me that they passed with money. They even boasted. It hurt, I cried. But I did not return to the village, and I vowed not to go until I entered school"[4. 92].

The second example: "I changed overnight. The institute is for money, the crime is for money, the job is for money, money, money, money ... everywhere the work is done only with money ... That night the image of money seemed to be hardly imprinted on my heart and mind. It was as if my veins were beating for money, for money ..."[4. 94].

So, the injustices in the society, the corruption in almost all spheres, cause a simple young man from the village to go astray and become their ally. The opportunity for the writer to state this bitter truth came only in the late 1980s, at a time when such injustices were eating away at Soviet society.

Perhaps there weren't many who blamed the mother when these things happened these days. Because the mother was the jeweler's daughter, her eyes were fixed on seeing the jewelry made by her father. Even in the city there is no one equal to him in determining the authenticity or falsity of gold jewelry, the probe, all shopkeepers and jewelers turn to him with confidence. Today, no one blames the successors or students of those jewelers. While artisans who weaved satin on their handicrafts at home during the Soviet era were imprisoned on charges of illegal activity, today there is a great deal of room for many different industries like theirs, which are supported by the state.

In fact, at all times except the Soviet era, making expensive gold and silver jewelry or various atlases and chimes at home, i.e., home-based work, was not considered a crime. It is natural that even hand-made products are of better quality than those made in factories, which means that they are more expensive. However, the root of the novel's events lies in the Soviet-era artificial shortages of traders, such as shopkeepers and warehouse managers, and officials who receive their "legitimate contributions" in a timely manner, those who

implement the anti-wealth policies of the poor government. According to Soviet policy, all products were to be manufactured in state-owned factories and sold at the same price everywhere. But in which store did the gold jewelry, which was supposed to be sold at the same price, and which was mostly bought for a dream, be sold at its own price? From which store did the parents, who were worried about marrying their son or evicting their daughter, buy atlases and chimes for their own price?

Consequently, all of this is a top-down government policy, i.e. an underwater part of the iceberg invisible to ordinary people. In the eyes of the common people, a warehouse manager is a criminal who does not give rare items to shopkeepers at his own cost, while a shopkeeper is accused of hiding rare items and selling them at a higher price in order to recover the bribe he paid to the warehouse manager. That is why it is natural that the working people, who live in houses, drive cars, and live on bribes, hate this category.

There are many similar dilemmas in the play. For example, not all law enforcement officers, police officers, investigators and judges, whose main task is to fight criminals, are equally honest, but many of them are accomplices of the accused liars. It is obvious that H. Tukhtaboev has witnessed such cases many times during his feuilleton activity. For this reason, he describes the events of the work with extreme objectivity.

Most importantly, the story is told in the language of Zafar, the second son of a father who is a gold-selling mother and a warehouse manager. becomes a huge artistic reality that ends up eating an unclean society. "After I got married in 1987 and lived independently, I bought a Saratov refrigerator for 180 sums from a household goods store for 200 sums," he said. Tukhtaboev's novel "Dark Eyes" once again confirms that the events of corruption, not just in the case of one family, but in society as a whole.

According to Professor A.Rasulov: Khudoiberdi Tukhtaboev's novels "Riding the Yellow Giant", "The Land of Sweet Melons", "Sad Eyes" have many adventures. Adventure is a continuous movement of a person in the whirlpool of life, a struggle for the goal. Hashimjan, it is said, begins an adventure in search of fame. His adventures at the Long Ear Pirim Shrine, with the police, and the destruction of the Yellow Giant are both interesting, complex, and enlightening. What about Akrom's amazing adventures? If they are more than Hashim, they are not less. Zafar has experienced the contradictions of life and difficult trials due to his fistfight. " [2.49]

In the course of the novel, the mother is caught red-handed while buying gold coins and selling jewelry made by jewelers, and the father is caught in the process of organized bribery. The mother, who was in constant danger of being caught red-handed in the gold trade and eventually contracted heart disease, dies during the investigation, the father is sentenced to eleven years in prison, and all their property and even their homes are confiscated. is done. The akakhonu opakhan, who promised to release them from prison, will be left on the sidelines, like ravens fighting for their lives. Four underage children are left homeless and on the streets.

Unable to bear the ordeal, Nigora's entire body became white and leprous, and Zufar, the third son to be abducted in an attempt to retake the Volga, had been killed in a car crash. Worse of all, the man who wrote the letter to the relevant authorities about his

parents was a disabled eldest son, Akbar, who was a truthful man. The teenager, tormented by a guilty conscience, first tries to hang himself, then sets his house on fire and kills himself. As Akbar wrote his deeds as a will to his brother, Zafar read the letter and found out that his brother was the cause of all the troubles that befell his family.

According to the Hero of Uzbekistan, well-known literary critic I. Gafurov: "It is probably difficult to explain Akbar's betrayal of his family from a public point of view. But Akbar can't stand the sight of his parents cheating. He tries to prevent future tragedies. But how can the crumbling building be supported by stiff shoulders? Akbar suffers immensely from the tragedies that befell his family, and eventually commits suicide to escape the unbearable blows and trials that have befallen him." [3.55]

People's Poet of Uzbekistan Anvar Obidjon thinks: "Is there another Pavlik Morozov? I am talking about Pavlik, who died after exposing the "crime" of his father, who put the interests of his family above the interests of the government, and became a book hero of the whole "Kyzylstan" pioneer students. Maybe it's Hamlet from Uzbekistan? Maybe we are not able to understand it yet? After all, isn't everyone interesting with their inner experiences, with the behaviors that are necessary only for themselves?" [1.66]

Indeed, it is natural that every reader, young and old, who reads the novel "Miserable Eyes", will have different ideas. Some may accuse Akbar of being an incompetent child who rebelled and betrayed his parents, some may justify him as a truthful person, some may blame Atoulo's teacher for making him a thinker in this way, and so on. The skill of the writer is that he neither justifies nor condemns Akbar, but only directs the reader to make judgments with an objective description of what is happening.

In our opinion, Anwar Abidjan's description of Akbar as "a child who has not seen a hadith" is closer to the truth and deserves to be accepted as a generalized opinion of many. Because, in any case, Akbar, a student of the Shura school, was immersed in the blood of communist morality, first instilled in this school and then by Atoulo, he wrote in our classical literature Not every investigator and judge knows that the statement in the letter that his parents were not imprisoned will not cost him a penny. That is why he allegedly writes a letter to the criminal investigation department of the regional police in order to protect his parents from further crimes. "In my letter, I asked them to call me to order, but not to imprison me," he wrote in a will to his brother Zafar [4.243-244]. But Akbar, after all, is an inexperienced young man who does not know that the Soviet police are not limited to call the perpetrator to order, but to uprooting the root of the crime and imprisoning the perpetrator without hesitation.

The chain of events of the novel revolves mainly around Zafar, who is both a living witness and a direct participant in the events that take place. For this reason, the fact that the events of the work are told in his own language fully justifies itself. Although Zafar, at first glance, seems to be a teenager who is just entering life, unaware of the hardships of life, when his parents are imprisoned, all the responsibilities of the family fall on his shoulders. Because his brother Akbar is paralyzed and unable to walk, his brother Zafar is very unstable by nature, and his sister Nigora is still very young. That's why everything will

happen in front of Zafar's eyes, until he meets with his parents in prison and decides what to do next to get out of prison, who to meet, and how much to pay.

That's why he's not very excited at first. Because: "My grandfather and mother were in such a mess and they said that their hair was gray. We do not have to be afraid. We have a good relationship with the older ones, the ones who sit and stand for a long time. If they make a mustache ... that's it. What about my aunt? I wonder why they both stared at each other all of a sudden? We don't have to worry about my mother either. Ha-ha, it's nice to be pushing ourselves. We have a lot, a lot of money. We also have gold. Will they work?! My aunt would often say, "Oh, you, you," people would say, "People are no longer worshipping God. Everyone now worships either money or an official. Money is a god, an official prophet. People are now waiting for God's help with money ... "[4. 20].

But things turn out the other way around, with their parents believing in them, receiving their constant gifts, flirting with each other for a while, pretending to be brothers and sisters, and "doing a mustache" all the work they always want. the words of the akahon-u opaxon, which ends, will remain here this time. As a result, the mother with a heart condition died before the end of the investigation, and the father was imprisoned for eleven years. As mentioned above, when a family is in crisis, the eldest son sets himself on fire and kills himself. the girl Nigora, unable to bear this mental suffering, became seriously ill, leaving only one son, Zafar, as the successor of the family.

Akbar's suicide by setting fire to the house is also based on the play. He tells his father the story in a book he is reading in Russian: "A young man named Konovalov complained to the prosecutor about his brother. Having made a complaint, the case has grown and now he is trying to save her. He could not save his brother, he was imprisoned. Now he had a guilty conscience. Eh-he, he is suffering so much ... He was trying to kill himself ... "(pp. 88-89). With this example, the writer seems to be hinting that Akbar's fate will end just like Konovalov's.

In our opinion, the author did not call Zafar's horse in vain. Because Victory in its own name is a victory, a symbol of victory. It is no coincidence that Zafar, a living witness to all that has happened, is seeking revenge on Sadir Badalovich, the city's shopping center director, Judge Muhamedov, and his wife, Ibad Khan, nicknamed "Aunt Qazi," for the tragedy. Because Badalov did not fulfill his promise to take the Volga in order to save his mother, he wrote letters of complaint to the higher authorities about Badalov and Mukhamedov, who were at the forefront of these crimes and received a large share from each of them. , and was eventually admitted to the insane asylum on their own initiative. When he is convinced that reaching the truth legally is not as easy as he thinks, he begins to take revenge. In the beginning of his novel, he says, "I was imprisoned when I was 16 years old. I should have been imprisoned. Here they are. Of course, you ask why someone arrested you for committing a crime, what kind of law it was. Please let the law rest. The laws are fair, they are fair, and my roommates, who sleep in dark and gloomy rooms, know this very well. . We all agree on this. If you were talking about law enforcement, advocates, and propagandists, I would have kissed you on the tongue. "

In literary criticism, this series of events is considered to be Zafar's adventures, but they are not just adventures, they are extremely horrible, even in the heart of the reader who reads the work, these horrible events create hatred for the society in which these events took place.

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